

Supplemental material Baak *et al.* A simple and robust reporter-based framework for deep functional characterization of PPAR γ mutants.

Table S1: PPRE sequences

PPRE	Sequence ¹
<i>Lpl</i>	<u>AAGA</u> AGGGGA A <i>AGGGCA</i>
<i>Cidec</i>	<u>CACT</u> AGGCAA G <i>AGGGCA</i>
<i>Angptl4</i>	<u>AAGT</u> AGGAGA A <i>AGGTCA</i>
Synthetic	<u>AACT</u> AGGTCA A <i>AGGTCA</i>

¹PPAR γ binding on 5' half site in bold; PPAR γ binding 5' extension site underlined, and; RXR α binding on 3' half site in italic.

Table S2: Primer sequences used for mutagenesis

Primer	Sequence
K347T_Fw	5'-GTA ACTCTCCTCACATATGGAGTCCACGAG-3'
K347T_Rv	5'-CTCGTGGACTCCATATGTGAGGAGAGTTAC-3'
P387S_Fw	5'-GAGCCTGCGAAAGAGTTTTGGTGACTTTATG-3'
P387S_Rv	5'-CATAAAGTCACCAAAACTCTTTCGCAGGCTC-3'
Q438P_Fw	5'-CCATTGAAGACATTCCAGACAACCTGCTAC-3'
Q438P_Rv	5'-GTAGCAGGTTGTCTGGAATGCTTCAATGG-3'
Q314E_Fw	5'-CATCTTTCAGGGCTGCGAGTTTCGCTCCGTGG-3'
Q314E_Rv	5'-CCACGGAGCGAAACTCGCAGCCCTGAAAGATG-3'
T475M_Fw	5'-CTCAGACAGATTGTCATGGAACACGTGCAGCTA-3'
T475M_Rv	5'-TAGCTGCACGTGTTCCATGACAATCTGTCTGAG-3'

Figure S1: Co-factor profiling of PPAR γ loss-of-function (LOF) and gain-of-function (GOF) mutants (101 cofactor peptides).

LOF

GOF